

Treasury Single Account and Public Fund Management: A Study of Selected Federal Government Parastatals in Nigeria

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to determine the impact of Treasury Single Account on Public Fund Management. The specific objectives include; examining the impact of Treasury Single Account on Accountability, Transparency and leakages of public funds. In order to achieve these objectives, the survey research design was adopted using primary data with the aid of a questionnaire distributed to selected federal government parastatals (NNPC and FIRS). Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the federal government parastatals used. Regression analysis and the simple percentage were used to analyze the questionnaire obtained. It was discovered, based on the findings of the study, that, Treasury Single Account has a significant relationship with Public fund management proxies combined. The study concluded that Treasury Single Account expectedly improve accountability and transparency and as well reduce leakages in the financial system. Hence, the adoption of TSA should be encouraged by immense public enlightenment and clarification around the significance of the policy in other to nurture its success, the government should also shelter as soon as probable the appropriate statutory support to aid the appropriate regulatory atmosphere which will drive the effective implementation of the TSA.

Keywords; Treasury Single Account, Accountability, Transparency and Financial Leakages

Introduction

In the era of spiraling oil revenue, little did the public care about the manner in which the Nigerian government appropriated financial resources at its disposal. In resonance, revenue imperative organs made it a habit of defrauding the government by converting public resources to private use. Within the disjointed public finance management

approach, the government lacked the aptitude to enforce financial regulation. Furthermore, the manual nature in which receipts and expenditure of the government was treated, led to the nonexistence of interface between relevant stakeholders. Amongst other numerous inconsistencies, under the pr regime it was almost impossible for the government to have at consolidated view and knowledge of the amount it had in the treasury. Hence, it was not uncommon for public officials to connive with banking executives, contractors and other individuals or firms to defraud the state.

The need for a unified structure of government bank accounts to enable consolidation and optimal utilization of government cash resources in Nigeria became fully enforced in 2015 by the President of Nigeria, Muhammadu Buhari. On the 9th of August, 2015 President Muhammadu Buhari directed all the Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) to close all their accounts domiciled in the commercial banks and transfer them to the federation account and gave September 15th, 2015 as deadline for total compliance. This independent revenue e-collection scheme is implemented under Treasury Single Account (TSA) initiative, which requires that government revenue collection, is put into a single account for proper cash management. According to Igbokwe-Ibeto, (2016), TSA is a public accounting system under which all government revenue, receipts and income are collected into one single account, usually maintained by the country's Central Bank. It is a bank account or a set of linked bank accounts through which the government transacts all its receipts and payments and gets a consolidated view of its cash position at any given time (Onyekpere, 2015). TSA is a process and tool for effective management of government's finances, banking and cash position. In accordance with the name, it pools and unifies all government accounts through a single treasury account. TSA was introduced to reduce the proliferation of bank accounts operated by MDAs and also to promote transparency and accountability among all organs of the government. Fatile and Adejuwon (2017) averred that TSA is a useful tool to establish centralized control over government revenue through effective cash management. It also enhances accountability and enables government to know how much is accruing to its accounts on a daily basis. TSA is believed to be an efficient and effective means of managing government revenue generation and system that provide and enforce sufficient self-control mechanism on revenue generation and budget implementation using a daily return from account balances of various MDAs into a central account (Adebisi & Okike, 2016).

TSA according to Ocheni (2016) also facilitates better fiscal and monetary policy coordination as well as better reconciliation of fiscal and banking data, which in turn improves the quality of fiscal information. Some of the laudable motives behind the

introduction of TSA in Nigeria is to promote accountability, financial discipline, and curb corrupt practices in the Nigerian public sector (Abdulrasheed, 2016). Accountability according to Ejere (2013) is the obligation of the administrators to give a satisfactory account of their performance and the manner in which they have exercised powers conferred on them. Accountability entails revealing, explaining and justifying what one does, or has done, or how one discharges one's responsibilities. It is a concept that is deeply rooted in political power and democracy linking the electorates with the executive to whom enormous power is entrusted. Accountability affords reliable accounting and financial reporting and allocation of resources. Inadequate accounting and reporting may however lead to corruption in the public sector. Corruption on the other hand has been a major factor that has been alleged to slow down the actualization of government policies and has also been said to lead to slow infrastructural development due to diversion of fund by public officers to personal pockets. Dong (2011) posits that public sector corruption means misuse of public office for private benefits. It is when a holder of public office motivated by private gain gives preferential treatment that is not officially approved. Corruption has remained one of the major threats to political and economic development in any economy.

Forgone, it is established that TSA was introduced to maximize the use of cash through concentration, accountability, reduction in float costs, corrupt practices and to enhance financial discipline in the public sector. This study is triggered to assess the extent to which TSA system can effectively handle these issues by examining the effect of treasury single account (TSA) on Nigerian public sector financial accountability. The directive by President Muhammadu Buhari that all revenues due to the Federal Government or any of its agencies must be paid into the Treasury Single Account (TSA) or designated accounts maintained and operated in the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has been described by many as a welcome development as it aims at fighting corruption and financial accountability in Nigeria (Yusuf & Mohammed, 2016). The Nigerian society according to Okwoli (2004) is packed with stories of wrong practices such as ghost workers on pay roll of ministries, extra-ministerial department and parastatals, fraud and embezzlement of public funds. Corruption has been like a cankerworm eating deep into the fabrics of the Nigerian system, keeping the country in a terribly precarious situation, despite the huge human and natural resources it possesses.

Bello (2001) also averred that there is a near total absence of the notion and ethics of accountability in the conduct of public affairs in Nigeria. This, according to Bello (2001), has created a variety of loopholes that have facilitated and sustained corrupt practices which

has been the bane of public sector financial mismanagement in Nigeria. TSA came into the picture as a system of combating corrupt practices, eliminating financial indiscipline in public finance and ensuring adequate fund flow that will be channelled to critical sectors of the economy to catalyse development. Theoretically, it is expected that TSA would bring about mutual benefit, halt economic injustice and engender financial discipline, transparency, accountability, and a new economic and political order in Nigeria. However, in the public sector management and political economy of Nigeria, its impact has been a mixed bag of the good, the bad and the ugly (Igbokwe-Ibeto, 2016).

The effect of TSA in the Nigerian public sector has received significant research attention though recently introduced. Adebisi and Okike (2016), Igbokwe-Ibeto, et al (2016), Oti, Igbeng and Obim (2016), Igbekoyi and Agbaje (2017) also examined this trend. However, most of these studies focused on the effect of TSA on corruption in the public sector with no studies specifically addressing the effect of treasury single account on financial management which is the gap the study is out to fill. This study therefore examines the effect of TSA on financial management in the selected parastatals in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of this study is to determine the extent to which the Treasury Single Account (TSA) has affected public fund management in Nigeria, using selected Federal government parastatals.

The following specific objectives are highlighted to:

1. analyze the impact of Treasury Single Account on accountability.
2. examine the effect of Treasury Single Account on transparency.
3. determine the effect of Treasury Single Account on financial leakages.

Statement of Hypotheses

H01 There is no significant relationship between treasury single account and financial accountability H02 There is no significant relationship between treasury single account and financial transparency. H03 There is no significant relationship between treasury single account and financial leakages.

Literature Review Treasury Single Account (TSA): A conceptual Analysis

The IMF working paper (2010) defined TSA as a unified structure of government bank account that gives a consolidated view of government cash resources. Based on the principle of unity of cash and unity of treasury, TSA is a bank account or a set of linked accounts through which the government transacts all its receipts and payments. According

to Chukwu (2015), a treasury single account (TSA) is a network of subsidiary accounts all linked to a main account such that, transactions are effected in the subsidiary accounts but closing balances on these subsidiary accounts are transferred to the main account, at the end of each business day. Treasury Single Account is a public accounting system under which all government revenue, receipts and income are collected into one single account, usually maintained by the country's Central Bank and all payments done through this Account as well (Yusuf, 2015).

It is a policy or monetary tool that increases the revenue inflow in the purse of the government as well as places it in a better stead to adequately meet its financial obligations to the citizens of the country. According to Oyedele (2015), TSA is a way of unifying various government's bank accounts to give a consolidated view of government cash resources. For Treasury Single Account (TSA) to work effectively there must be daily clearing of and consolidation of cash balance into the central account even where the MDA's accounts are already held at the CBN. However, this objective can be achieved through proper accounting rather than by holding cash in separate bank accounts. TSA therefore covers all funds including votes and extra-budgetary accounts or even funds held in trust by government. To actualize, this aim, accounting system must be robust and capable of accurately distinguishing trust assets in the TSA.

From the forgoing, it is established that, a treasury single account is a public accounting system under which all government revenue, receipts and income are collected into one single account, usually maintained by the country's Central Bank and all payments done through this account as well. The purpose is primarily to ensure accountability of government revenue, enhance transparency and avoid misapplication of public funds. The maintenance of a Treasury Single Account will help to ensure proper cash management by eliminating idle funds usually left with different commercial banks and in a way enhance reconciliation of revenue collection and payment. Accountability is all about being answerable to those who have invested their trust, faith and resources to someone. Adegite (2010) defined accountability as the obligation to demonstrate that work has been conducted in accordance with agreed rules and standard, and the officer reports fairly and accurately on performance results vis-à-vis mandated roles and or/plans. It means doing things transparently in line with due process and the provision of feedback. In ethics and governance, accountability is answerability, blame worthiness, liability, and the expectation of account-giving. As an aspect of governance, it has been centred to discussions related to problems in the public sector.

Corruption is a phenomenon plaguing both public and private sectors of most economies and it is not restricted to a particular country or region. According to McShane and Nilsson (2010), corruption is when a holder of public office motivated by private gain gives preferential treatment that is not officially approved. McShane and Nilsson (2010) explained that public sector corruption means misuse of public office for private benefits. Corruption undermines development by distorting the rule of law and weakening the institutional foundation on which economic growth depends. Corruption is not peculiar to developing nations alone. It is a plague that affects both developed and developing economy, although the occurrence in developing societies like Nigeria seems to be pervasive. Dada (2014) asserted that corruption seems to be the most popular issue discussed as a cause of underdevelopment in Nigeria today. Almost every section of the country is affected by corruption ranging from the education sector to the various organs of government. Corruption is the largest single inhibitor of equitable economic development in many countries of the world including Nigeria.

Corruption is an act which deviates from the formal rules of conduct governing the actions of someone in a position of public authority because of private, regarding - motive such as wealth, power or status. Corruption is the perversion of integrity or state of affairs through bribery, favour or moral depravity. In other words, corruption is a systematic vice in an individual, society or a nation which reflects favouritism, nepotism, tribalism, sectionalism, undue enrichment, amassing of wealth, abuse of office, power, position and derivation of undue gains and benefits, bribery, smuggling, fraud, illegal payments, money laundering, drug trafficking, falsification of documents and records, window dressing, false declaration, evasion, underpayment, deceit, forgery, concealment, aiding and abetting of any kind to the detriment of another person, community, society or nation.

Public financial discipline is concerned with the planning, organizing, procurement and utilization of government financial resources. Premchand (1999) sees public financial discipline as the link between the community's aspirations with resources, and the present with future. It lies at the very heart of the operations and fiscal policy of government. Financial discipline in the public sector has to do with adequate public financial management. Public. Adequate financial management according to Onuorah and Appah (2012) involves budget formulation, budget structures, payment system, government accounting and financial reporting and audit. The budget formulation is the step that involves the allocation of resources before the submission to the legislature for review and final approval. According to Onuorah and Appah (2012), in Nigeria, the budget formulation involves the articulation of the fiscal, monetary, political, economic, social and

welfare objectives of the government by the President; based on; (i) the department issues policies and guidelines which form the basis of circulars to Ministries/Departments requesting for inputs and their needs for the ensuring fiscal periods; (ii) accounting officers of responsibility units are required to obtain and collate the needs of their units; and (iii) accounting officers of ministries, in this case the Permanent Secretaries, are required to collate these proposals which would be defended by unit heads before the supervising minister. From the foregone, it is established that financial discipline is how well funds are being spent in line with budgets and clearly spelt out financial policies.

Reasons for Treasury Single Account (TSA)

Ocheni in Nelson and Oriaho, (2016) maintains that prior to the implementation of the TSA; government was incurring financial cost on debit balances in some MDAs accounts, while it was earning close to nothing on the credit balances of other MDAs. The idea of treasury account came into being when some agencies refused to declare and remit the 25 percent of their annual revenue they generated to the treasury as demanded by law. In 2012 about N120 billion was forcefully collected by government from MDAs being 25 percent of their gross revenue to the treasury with another N34 billion collected in 2013. Before then most the MDAs were reluctant to remit the requested amount by law to the treasury (Daily Trust Editorial, 2015:16 in Bashir, 2016). Furthermore, the Revenue Mobilization and Fiscal Commission released an audit report which indicted some banks for withholding about N12billion revenue collected on behalf of the Nigerian Customs Services and Federal Inland Revenue Service. The revenue according to the commission is stashed in 19 banks from January 2008 to June 2012. The chairman, Non-oil Committee of the Commission, Rev. Ajibola Fagboyegun demanded for urgent return of the funds by the banks to avoid sanctions (Hamisu, 2015).

According to the Guardian Editorial (2015), the Federal establishments affected by the directives are all fully funded organs of government, ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs), foreign missions and partly funded government establishment like teaching hospitals, medical centers and tertiary institutions. Others include the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Security and Exchange Commission (SEC), Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC), Nigerian Port Authority (NPA), Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC), Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN), Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA). The list of affected organs also has National Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC), National Shippers Council (NSC) Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), Nigerian Customs Services (NCS), Ministry of Mines and Steel Development (MMSD) and the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR), Nigeria Immigration Service(NIS), among others.

Modus operandi of TSA

According to Oyedele (2015), for TSA to work effectively there must be daily clearing of and consolidation of cash balances into the central account even where the MDA's accounts are already held at the CBN such as the FIRS. TSA can cover all funds earmarked and budgetary accounts or even funds held in trust by government. To make this work, accounting systems must be robust and capable of accurately distinguishing trust assets in the TSA. The Central Bank of Nigeria has opened a consolidated Revenue Account to receive all government revenue and effect payments through this account. All Ministries, Departments and Agencies are expected to remit their revenue collections to this account through the individual commercial banks who act as collection agents. This means that the money deposit banks will continue to maintain revenue collection accounts for MDA's but all monies collected by these banks will have to be remitted to the Consolidated Revenue Accounts with the CBN at the end of each banking day. (Rock, 2015).

In other words, MDA's accounts with money deposit banks must be zeroed at the end of every banking day by a complete remittance to the TSA of all revenue collected. Different types of account could be maintained under a TSA arrangement, and these may include the TSA main account, subsidiary or subaccounts, transaction accounts and zero balance account. Other types of accounts that could be operated include imprest accounts, transit accounts and correspondence accounts. These accounts are maintained for transaction purposes for funds flowing in and out of the TSA. Ahmed (2016) describes the following as various accounts under Treasury Single Account (TSA)

TSA Main Account. This is the treasury's account with the central bank, which consolidates the government's cash position. It is the main TSA account when the TSA arrangement in a particular country consists of a set of linked accounts. Cash balances in all other linked accounts are swept into this account. In other words, all government receipts finally flow into, and all disbursements are met from, the central TSA account.

TSA Subsidiary Accounts or Sub-accounts

These are not separate bank accounts per se (in the sense of holding individual cash balances), but are special subaccounts within the main TSA account. This is basically an accounting arrangement to group together a set of transactions and allows the government to maintain the distinct accounting identity or ledger of its budget organizations (line ministries/agencies) effectively. A cash disbursement ceiling for each entity can be enforced against these ledgers. Balances in these accounts are netted off with the TSA main account for cash management purposes.

Transaction Accounts

Sometimes government bank accounts that are justified for retail transaction banking operations are opened separately and structured as transaction accounts. These separate transaction accounts could be opened for government entities that need transaction banking services, but do not have a direct access to the TSA main account or a subsidiary account, and/or specific category of operations (e.g., special funds). A transaction account could take the form of a zero-balance account or an imprest account.

Zero-balance accounts (ZBAs)

Where transactional accounts are necessary, these are generally opened on a zero-balance basis, i.e., end-of-the day cash balances in these accounts are swept back into the TSA main account periodically (preferably daily). Such accounts opened in commercial banks are used for disbursements or for collection of government revenues (particularly nontax revenues). At the end of the day, all revenues collected would be deposited in the TSA. The commercial bank would honor payments of the respective agency and would be reimbursed by the TSA overnight. ZBAs have many similarities with special credit line arrangements, where budget agencies are provided spending credits towards the amount of payments they can make within a specified period, to be reimbursed by the TSA in the central bank. A ZBA also has the benefit that it bypasses the normal interbank settlement process for each individual transaction, which is often time consuming in developing countries, and ensures same-day settlement on a net basis for all receipts and payments passing through the accounts. (Adamu, 2016).

Imprest accounts

These transaction accounts can hold cash up to a maximum authorized amount and are recouped from time to time. Such accounts might be necessary in some cases, particularly when there is only limited availability of interbank settlement facilities. However, the number of imprest accounts should be kept to a minimum and the strategy should be to progressively transform these accounts into zero-

Transit accounts

These accounts are not meant for day-to-day transaction banking operations of government units. A transit account simply serves as a transit for eventual flow of cash into the TSA main account. Transit accounts might be necessary for major revenue streams to monitor their collection and remittance by the banking system and to facilitate revenue sharing (formula-based sharing from a common pool of resources) between tiers of government in a federal system in line with constitutional provisions.

Correspondent Accounts

A separate ledger account is opened for each correspondent. The correspondent entity has real-time information on the balances it maintains in the TSA. There should be safeguards to ensure that each correspondent government is provided with the funds needed to implement its own budget in a timely manner. The central bank (which maintains the accounts in the TSA) has the obligation to make payments to the extent of the balances available in a correspondents account. (Including the required ex ante control for authorizing payments). (Adamu, 2016).

Prospects of TSA

The prospects of TSA as contained in IMF (2010), Ahmed (2016) and Othman (2016) are outlined as follows:

1. **It Allows Complete and Timely Information on Government Cash Resources.** In countries with advanced payment and settlement systems and an Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS) with adequate interfaces with the banking system, this information will be available in real time. A minimum, complete updated balance should be available daily.
2. **Improves Appropriation Control.** The TSA ensures that the MoF has full control over budget allocations and strengthens the authority of the budget appropriation. When separate bank accounts are maintained, the result is often a fragmented system, where additional cash resources that become available through various creative, often extra budgetary, measures augment funds provided for budgetary appropriations.
3. **Improves Operational Control During Budget Execution.** When the treasury has full information about cash resources, it can plan and implement budget execution in an efficient, transparent, and reliable manner. The existence of uncertainty regarding whether the treasury will have sufficient funds to finance programmed expenditures may lead to sub-optimal behavior by budget entities, such as exaggerating their estimates for cash needs or channeling expenditures through off-budget arrangements.
4. **Enables Efficient Cash Management.** A TSA facilitates regular monitoring of government cash balances. It also enables higher quality cash outturn analysis to be undertaken (e.g., identifying causal factors of variances and distinguishing causal factors from random variations in cash balances)
5. **Reduces Bank Fees and Transaction Costs.** Reducing the number of bank accounts results in lower administrative costs for the government for maintaining these accounts, including the cost associated with bank reconciliation, and reduced

banking fees (Othman. 2016).

6. **Facilitates Efficient Payment Mechanisms.** A TSA ensures that there is no ambiguity regarding the volume or the location of the government funds and makes it possible to monitor payment mechanisms precisely. It can result in substantially lower transaction costs because of economies of scale in processing payments. The establishment of a TSA is usually combined with elimination of the “float” in the banking and the payment systems, and the introduction of transparent fee and penalty structures for payment services. Many governments have achieved substantial reductions in their real cost of banking services by introducing a TSA.(Ahmed, 2016).
7. **Improves Bank Reconciliation and Quality of Fiscal Data.** A TSA allows for effective reconciliation between the government accounting systems and cash flow statements from the banking system. This reduces the risk of errors in reconciliation processes and improves the timeliness and quality of the fiscal accounts.
8. **Lowers Liquidity Reserve Needs.** A TSA reduces the volatility of cash flows through the treasury, thus allowing it to maintain lower cash reserve/buffer to meet unexpected fiscal volatility (IMF, 2010) Economic Highlights (2015), summarizes the prospects of TSA as follows.
 1. TSA will promote transparency and facilitate compliance with sections 80 and 162 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.
 2. With TSA all receipts due to government or its agencies will be paid into TSA resident in Central Bank of Nigeria [CBN].
 3. Since TSA is a unified structure of government bank accounts, it enables consolidation and optimal utilization of government's cash resources.
 4. TSA provides a consolidated view of government's cash position always.
 5. The CBN, SEC, CAC and NPA, NCC as well as FAAN and NCAA, NIMASA, NDIC, NSC, NNPC, FIRS, NCS, MMSD, DPR and other government agencies will implement TSA.
 6. When linked to TSA, the accounting system will be configured to allow the agencies access to funds based on their approved budgetary provisions.
 7. The implementation of TSA brings transparency, efficiently and accountability.
 8. TSA is part of the public financial management reforms under pillar three of the National Strategy for Public Service Reforms towards vision 20:2020
 9. TSA addresses impediments to effective and efficient cash management.
 10. TSA ends problems of fragmented banking, which affected government's ability to undertake efficient cash planning and management as required by the Fiscal Responsibility Act. With TSA, government can track its expenditure in a timely manner.

11. TSA makes it possible for flexible operations, contrary to past regime where officers must get to their desks before effecting transactions.
12. TSA enables online real time transactions. Meaning, payment can be made from any point in the world.
13. TSA instills fiscal discipline and prudence as over 1,000 dormant or idle accounts will remain shut.
14. With TSA, the average monthly overdrafts with the CBN fell from the overdrawn amount of N102 billion in December 2011 to N4.461 billion credit in September 2012 with 93 MDAs out of over 400 (Economic Highlights, 2015)

Challenges of TSA

1. **Uneasy calm in the Banking sector:** The TSA policy is fraught with apprehension and uneasy calm. This is because of the withdrawal of public sector funds which constitute a large chunk of commercial banks deposits. TSA have led to the closure of about 10, 000 multiple bank accounts operated by MDAs in commercial banks and that HAS led to bank employees being apprehensive about their future.
2. **Use of government funds:** The mopping up of public sector funds from the commercial banks as directed by the TSA policy will stop banks from enjoying government's fund deposit especially fixed deposit that help them to invest and reap hefty dividends. Some of these funds are sometimes not withdrawn for six months or even more and banks trade with them and make a profit.
3. **Loss of Investment:** With the full implementation of TSA, the era of government money being lent back to government or invest in forex speculations will no longer be feasible.
4. **Fall in interest rate:** With TSA, government can guarantee its revenue and the implication is to force interest rates to naturally nosedive, since no serious business should be willing to borrow at a double digit interest rates when the economy is struggling at between 4 and 5 percent.
5. **Deposit wars:** TSA implementation triggers deposit wars amongst banks. Each DMBs will device means of mobilizing funds from the private sector and that will see the return of the era when women are engaged by banks specifically for deposit mobilization and that encourages the use of any means necessary to meet target.
6. **Increase in deposit interest rate:** The implementation of TSA will force banks to increase the deposit interest rate as a means of inducing customers and cause drop in the lending rate and profitability of banks.(Economic Highlights, 2015)

Empirical Review

Adebisi and Okike (2016) studied the adoption of the treasury single account (TSA) and its effect on revenue leakages of Nigerian states. Primary data were collected via questionnaire while the analysis was done using regression analysis with the aid of SPSS 22. The result of the study revealed that the TSA adoption is an effective tool for curbing revenue leakages in Nigerian states.

Yusuf and Mohammed (2016) examined the effect of (TSA) policy on the public financial management in Nigeria and its benefits if properly implemented. Both primary and secondary data were employed. The population of this study comprised of Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) within Damaturu, Yobe State. The data were analyzed using ANOVA techniques. The result of the study showed that, proper implementation of TSA by all stakeholders will help tremendously in reducing corruption, mismanagement of Public fund, block leakages and other financial irregularities in states and the country at large.

Igbokwe-Ibeto, et al (2016) evaluated the policy of Treasury Single Account (TSA) adopted by the Nigerian government as an essential tool for enhancing transparency and accountability in public sector financial. The study adopted both qualitative and quantitative research design and descriptive analysis to gain an insight into the nature and character of TSA operations in Nigeria. The study found that, for an administration that has social contract with Nigerians in terms of service delivery; it has the obligation to aggregating states' resources to provide social services, amenities, and infrastructural development to the people.

Oti, Igbeng and Obim (2016) appraised the policy impact of TSA in Nigeria with a view to proffering solution to the identified gaps. Questionnaires were administered to gather views of individuals and institutions. Secondly, data were equally gathered and analyzed using survey and exploratory research design. The study revealed various sheds of opinion: while bankers decry the distortion of their liquidity management plan, the federal government on the other hand claims a huge success because it can now comment on its aggregate cash holding without the drudgery hitherto associated with getting to all commercial banks or MDAs with multiple accounts.

Yusuf and Mohammed (2016) examined the effect of treasury single account policy on the public financial management in Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of Ministries, Departmentand Agencies (MDAs) within Bauchi metropolis using a sample of

72 respondents through judgment sampling. The data were analyzed using the Pearson Correlation techniques. The result of this research showed that adoption of a Treasury Single Account (TSA) is capable of plugging financial loopholes, promoting transparency and accountability in the public Financial System.

Igbekoyi and Agbaje (2017) assessed the implication of adoption of TSA on accountability and transparency in the Nigerian public sector; with a view to find out if the policy is capable of promoting government accountability function. The study consisted of all ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs) in the public service with sample size of ten (10) MDAs involved in revenue generation selected using purposive sampling technique. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis (ANOVA). The finding of the study showed that, TSA significant positive impact on financial leakages, transparency, and curb financial misappropriation.

Fatile and Adejuwon (2017) examined the implication of Treasury Single Account on cost of governance with specific reference to Buhari civilian administration in Nigeria. The study was qualitative in nature, relying on secondary sources. It was anchored on Stakeholder Theory. The study found that increase in the cost of governance is not basically as a result of over-bloated bureaucracy rather corruption can be considered major cause of the increase. TSA therefore is primarily to ensure accountability of government revenue, enhance transparency and avoid misappropriation of public funds.

Nwaorgu and Ezenwaka (2017) ascertained the effect of treasury single account and accountability in the Nigeria Public Sector. A descriptive survey research design was used. The population of this study consisted of 600 staff of the four federal health tertiary institutions drawn from Account Departments and simple size of 250 Account Departments staffs were selected using the proportionate random sampling technique. A structured 25-item validated questionnaire was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was ensured using pilot test technique, which was analyzed using Cronbach alpha method and yielded an overall reliability co-efficient of 0.85 with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) 20.0. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and one regression model for the research questions and for test of hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings showed that adaptation of a treasury single account and accountability (TSA) in the Nigeria Public Sector is capable of plugging financial.

Loopholes, promoting transparency and accountability in Federal Health Tertiary Institutions in SouthEast Nigeria. Akujuru and Enyioko (2017) examined the effects of

treasury single account policy on corruption in Nigeria from 2011 to 2017. The study adopted a cross sectional survey design and used a questionnaire to generate its data. The population of the study consisted of 6393 staff from the federal ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was determined at 377 staff through the use of Prof. Taro Yameme sample size method. The data were analyzed through the use of descriptive statistics. The study found that the treasury single account (TSA) policy was introduced to block financial leakages, reduce corruption, promote transparency and prevent mismanagement of government's revenue in public sector organizations.

It is Therefore established that majority of the studies focused on the effect of TSA on financial management in the public sector with few studies specifically addressing its effect on accountability, corrupt practices especially from the Benue state perspective. This study therefore examines the effect of TSA on accountability, corrupt practices and financial discipline in the Nigerian public sector.

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on stakeholder theory. The stakeholder theory was popularized by Richard Edward Freeman in 1970. The main idea behind Freeman's Stakeholder Approach was to try to build a framework that was responsive to the concerns of managers who were being confronted with unprecedented levels of environmental turbulence and change. The theory holds that the purpose of the firm is to create wealth or value for its stakeholders by converting their stakes into goods and services or to serve as a vehicle for coordinating stakeholder interests.

The word Stakeholder was chosen on the basis of the traditional term – stockholder, which takes only a look at the economic point of view, where the stakeholders are defined as any group of individuals who is affected by or can affect the achievement of an organization's objectives (Freeman, 1984). Freeman (1984) further states that stakeholder approach suggests that managers must formulate and implement processes which satisfy all and only those groups who have a stake in the business. A stakeholder approach is very much concerned about active management of the business environment, relationships, and the promotion of shared interests in order to develop business strategies. The theory assumed that adoption of Treasury Single Account by the federal government is as a result of the pressure from stakeholders/citizens majorly against corruption. It suggested that the government will respond to the concerns and expectations of powerful stakeholders/citizens and some of the responses will be in the form of strategic opinions.

Stakeholders' theory provides rich insights into the factors that motivate government in relation to the adoption and implementation of Treasury Single Account (Ekubiat & Ime, 2016).

Research Methodology

This study adopted a survey method. The survey method was employed, and this certainly allowed the researcher to make more reliable conclusions on the present effect of TSA on accountability, transparency and financial leakages in Parastatals like Nigerian National Petroleum Cooperation (NNPC), Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS)

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The population of the study is one thousand three hundred and seven (1307) in the office of the Accountant General and Auditor General's Headquarter Abuja. This population includes; top, middle, junior and management staff because of the mandate of checkmating financial transaction of Federal Parastatals.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique Taro Yamane Formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n=sample size

N=total population size

1 is constant

e = the assumed error margin or tolerable error which is taken as 5% (0.05)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{1307}{1 + 1307(0.05)^2} = \frac{1307}{3.27} = \underline{400}$$

Sample size = 400

Data Presentation and Analysis and presentation of findings was carried out using statistical software which includes SPSS version 24 and Microsoft Excel. These software aided in the generation of suitable charts and tables which were used in drawing conclusions as well as presenting the research findings. The study used **simple regression analysis** to test the statistical significance of the independent variables on the dependent variables. Regression is an important approach to modeling the relationship between the dependent variable (y) and one or more independent variable (x). A regression equation describes how the mean value of a response variable relates to specific values of the predictor variables (Bhattacharyya, 2011).

Table 3. Data from Primary Source and Discussion

Returned	346	87
Unreturned	54	13
Total	400	100

The above table shows that out of 400 questionnaires administered to the staff of Immigration service in the headquarter, only 346 representing 87% were completed and returned, while 54 questionnaires representing 13% of the questionnaires were not returned. The 346 returned questionnaires were used for the analysis.

The Model Used for the Study

$$TSA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACC + \beta_2 TRC + \beta_3 LKG + \varepsilon$$

Where: TSA = Treasury Single Account, ACC=Accountability, TRC=Transparency, LKG =Financial Leakages β_0 = Constant, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients and ε = Regression error Ordinary least square of multiple regression analysis was used to estimate the equation above.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistical Table for Dependent and Independent Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Error	Statistic	Error
TSA	340	1.00	5.00	3.0363	1.21541	-.121	.132	-.954	.264
ACC	340	1.00	5.00	3.2186	1.12752	-.142	.132	-.902	.264
TRC	340	1.00	5.00	3.2480	1.06226	-.302	.132	-.736	.264
LKG	340	1.00	5.00	3.4108	.91684	-.318	.132	-.424	.264
Valid N (listwise)	340								

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The descriptive statistics table above shows the average scored for treasury single account (TSA), accountability (ACC), Transparency (TRC) and financial leakages (LKG) is 3.0363, 3.2186, 3.2480 and 3.4108 respectively of pension fund scheme toward transparency and accountability. The minimum reach is 1 and the maximum reach is 5 in all the respective cases. The Skewness and Kurtosis values in the table in all respective cases indicate that data were normally distributed.

Table 2: Correlations Matrix of Independent Variables

		PFA	PFC	PFN
ACC	Pearson Correlation	1	.198**	.601**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	340	340	340
TRC	Pearson Correlation	.198**	1	.617**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	340	340	340
LKG	Pearson Correlation	.601**	.617**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	340	340	340

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The correlation analysis of the variables above depicts the relationship of accountability (ACC), Transparency (TRC) and financial leakages (LKG). The correlation of the variables is significant since the probability values (0.000) of all the variables are less than 0.05 significance level, it is therefore revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between the variables. This implies that all the variables move in the same direction.

Regression Result showing the Effect of TSA on ACC, TRC and LKG

Table 3: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.790 ^a	.624	.619	.56571	1.890

- a. Predictors: (Constant), TSA
- b. Dependent Variable: ACC, TRC, LKG

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 3 above is the model summary that indicates the Regression Coefficient (R) and the Coefficient of Determination (R²). The Regression Coefficient (R) of 0.790 shows a good positive correlation between the variables, while the Coefficient of Determination (R²) of 0.624 indicates that about 62% of variation in treasury single account can be explained by the combined effects of ACC, TRC and LKG and the remaining 42% can be explained by other variables did not include this study. These results has proved that the model is well fitted and useful for the purpose of explaining and predicting the relationship between the combined variables. The Durbin-Watson value of 1.890 from the table indicates the absence of autocorrelation among the variables.

Table 4: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	177.751	4	44.438	138.856	.000 ^b
	Residual	107.209	335	.320		
	Total	284.960	339			

- a. Dependent Variable: ACC, TRC, LKG
- b. Predictors: (Constant), TSA **Source: Field Survey, 2022**

Table 4 presents the ANOVA results. The results indicate the fitness of the model. The F-statistics value of 138.856 with its corresponding P-value (sig. value) of 0.000 from the table indicates that the model is fit.

Table 5: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	.988	.113		8.771	.000		
PFA	.184	.033	.244	5.529	.000	.579	1.728
PFC	.093	.042	.114	2.192	.029	.415	2.411
PFN	.446	.049	.516	9.059	.000	.346	2.894

- a. Dependent Variable: PFT **Source: Field Survey, 2022**

Table 5 is the Coefficients table from which the regression line is extracted. The regression line $ACC = 0.988 + 0.184PFA + 0.093PFC + 0.446PFN$ indicates that accountability improves by 0.988% for every 1% increase in independent variables (TSA). The ACC value of 0.184 indicates that the size of effect TSA has on ACC in selected parastatals is 0.184 (18.4%), the TRC value of 0.93 indicates that the size of effect TSA has on TRC in the selected parastatals is 0.93 (9.3%), while the LKG value of 0.446 indicates that the size of effect TSA has on LKG in the selected parastatals is 0.446 (44.6%). The Standardized Coefficients (Beta) values of 0.244, 0.114 and 0.516 respectively, indicates that PFN has more effect on ACC with 0.516 (51.6%) followed by TRC with 0.244 (24.4%) and LKG has the least effect on PFT with 0.114 (11.4%). The respective P-values of 0.000, 0.029 and 0.000 indicate that the effect is significant at 5% level of significant. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values of 1.728, 2.411 and 2.894 indicate that the explanatory variables are not highly correlated. These, therefore, show absence of multicollinearity among the independent variables since multicollinearity exists only when the VIF Value is greater than 10.

Findings

Independently, Treasury Single Account has a positive significant relationship on transparency at a level of significance of 000.0 which is less than p-value of 0.05. The result also indicated that Treasury Single Account has a positive relationship with financial transparency and financial leakages of public funds. Therefore, the study rejected the three null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The independent variable Treasury Single Account has statistical significance on the dependent variables which are accountability, transparency and financial leakages of public funds. Findings of this study, therefore, provide insight into the effect of Treasury Single Account on public fund management. It further provided an insight as to the extent to which the independent variable affects each dependent variable and also provides and with an affirmation of the extent to which the variations in each dependent variable are caused by the independent variable covered in the models as depicted by the R square. The study concludes that Treasury Single Account has a significant positive relationship to public fund management.

Recommendations

1. Overall, the implementation of TSA should be progressive for the economy in general. The Suitable authorities will have to now clinch transparency, limpidity and accountability more than ever before.
2. Government should engross in immense public enlightenment and clarification around the significance of the policy to nurture its success. Financial transparency always improve financial accountability.
3. The government should shelter as soon as probable the appropriate statutory support to aid the appropriate regulatory atmosphere which will drive the effective implementation of the TSA to avoid financial leakage in the system.

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